

On the Evaluation of the Reaction Rate Constant in Chromic Acid Oxidations

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We have reinvestigated the problem of estimating the true first order rate constant in the chromic acid oxidations. This analysis was necessitated by the fact that if HCrO_4^- is an active oxidation species then the reaction rate constants should increase with the progress of the reaction because the proportion of HCrO_4^- in the solution increases with dilution and the wealth of relevant literature claims that the experimental rate constant remains practically constant with the progress of the reaction. Our analysis reveals why these two contradictions coexist and why no significant error gets incorporated in the customary procedure to compute the corrected rate constant.

Chromic acid is one of the most versatile oxidants and is extensively used both in synthetic and kinetic investigations¹⁻³. From the mechanistic point of view it offers certain interesting features. Indeed, single step three-electron transfers in chromic acid oxidations have been reported⁴ but one- and two-electron steps are overwhelmingly common^{5,6}. This means that intermediate oxidation states of chromium also participate in these oxidations⁷.

The other feature which adds to the complexity of chromic acid oxidations and to which we are concerned herein is that in aqueous solution chromium(vi) exists in several protolytic and hydrolytic equilibria¹. The species involved in them are $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, HCr_2O_7^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, H_2CrO_4 , HCrO_4^- , CrO_4^{2-} etc. Hence, it is obvious to enquire, which of these species are the active oxidants. However, in moderately acidic aqueous solutions, the only chromium(vi) species which exist are HCrO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and they exist in the following equilibria,

and the corresponding equilibrium constant K_D , has the usual expression¹,

$$K_D = \frac{[\text{HCrO}_4^-]^2}{[\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}]} = 2.3 \times 10^{-2} M \quad (25^\circ) \quad (2)$$

Thus our query reduces to know whether HCrO_4^- is an active oxidation species or it is $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ or both. The literature on chromic acid oxidations reports seemingly opposing observations. According to the findings of Westheimer³ and Best *et al.*⁸, with the progress of reaction the experimental pseudo-first order rate constant increases. On the other hand, almost all the later studies claim that the plots of logarithm of the total chromium(vi) concentration at time t of the reacting solution with time t produce fairly good straight-lines up to about 70–80% conversion under the condition of a large excess concentration of other reactants over chromium(vi).

In view of the above fact we have reinvestigated this problem. Our analysis reveals certain intricacies involved therein but in the end shows that the commonly adopted practice of obtaining a corrected rate constant (as described in the next section) of the reaction does not harm the quality of the results alarmingly.

The details of the problem :

When for chromium(vi) concentration a good first order plot is obtained up to 70–80% conversion, then the experimental rate law is

$$-\frac{d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = k_{\text{exp}}[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] \quad (3)$$

But if HCrO_4^- is an active oxidation species participating in the rate determining step, then the rate law is given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = k_{\text{corr}}[\text{HCrO}_4^-] \quad (4)$$

where, k_{exp} and k_{corr} are the respective pseudo-first order rate constants. Hence it is now a common practice to obtain the corrected rate constant as

$$k_{\text{corr}} = \frac{k_{\text{exp}} [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_0}{[\text{HCrO}_4^-]_0} \quad (5)$$

on computing initial rates from eqns.(3) and (4). In eqn.(5), the subscript 0 stands for the initial concentration. Indeed this procedure gives a fairly constant values of k_{corr} almost in all cases in which HCrO_4^- participates in the rate-limiting step.

However, the above methodology does not seem to be a sound one. We raise the following two questions. (a) When the experimental rate constant depends on the initial chromium(vi) concentration (*cf.* eqn. 5) then the former cannot remain constant during the course of a single kinetic run. This is so because the chromium(vi) concentration continuously decreases in a kinetic run making higher proportions of HCrO_4^- species available for the reaction (*cf.* Table 1). (b) In view of the (a), how one can obtain a

TABLE I-VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANTS WITH $[Cr^{VI}]$ IN CHROMIC ACID OXIDATION

$[Cr^{VI}]$ $\times 10^3 M$	$[HCrO_4^-]$ $\times 10^3 M$	k_{exp}^a	$\langle k_{exp} \rangle^b$		$\langle k_{corr} \rangle = \langle k_{exp} \rangle \frac{[Cr^{VI}]_0}{[HCrO_4^-]_0}$	
			75%	50%	75%	50%
0.5	0.480	0.960 k_1	-	-	-	-
1.0	0.927	0.927 k_1	-	0.893 k_1	-	0.963 k_1
2.0	1.74	0.870 k_1	0.840 k_1	0.814 k_1	0.964 k_1	0.935 k_1
4.0	3.14	0.785 k_1	0.738 k_1	0.700 k_1	0.940 k_1	0.891 k_1
6.0	4.35	0.725 k_1	-	-	-	-
8.0	5.71	0.714 k_1	0.662 k_1	0.643 k_1	0.927 k_1	0.900 k_1
10.0	6.41	0.641 k_1	0.584 k_1^c	-	0.911 k_1^c	-

^aComputed using eqn. (17) of the main text.

^bComputed using eqn. (18) of the main text for 75% and 50% conversions.

^cValues related to 80% conversion.

reasonably acceptable and constant values of k_{exp} from the data on a single kinetic run becomes an obvious query. Recall that, whether one uses the chemical or spectrophotometric methods to estimate chromium(vi) concentration it is not possible to experimentally estimate in a reaction mixture the concentration only of either $HCrO_4^-$ or $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ by the usual means. That is one obtains from experiments :

$$[Cr^{VI}] = [HCrO_4^-] + 2 [Cr_2O_7^{2-}] \quad (6)$$

Analysis of the problem :

The first named objection, namely (a), is generally made ineffective in two ways. In one of the approaches one measures the initial rates only, so that the change in total chromium(vi) concentration is within 5–10% of the total conversion. However, it is not always feasible to obtain a sufficiently accurate set of data within the initial 5–10% of the reaction, this is particularly so when one follows the chemical methods to estimate the total chromium(vi) concentration time to time. The second option is to restrict the investigations only to those chromium(vi) concentrations wherein $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ exists in insignificant amounts compared to $HCrO_4^-$ (cf. columns 1 and 2 of the Table 1). This is usually maintained by an upper limit of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ of total initial chromium(vi) concentration⁵. However, this practice is judicious on one count but is not advisable in general. In this option we eliminate $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ species from the reaction scene and hence one loses an opportunity to a possible probe into the reactivity patterns of this species. Thus $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ chemistry thereby suffers. We recall that there are experimental evidences suggesting a direct participation of $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ in certain reactions⁹.

Now let us turn our attention to the second query, namely, (b). On substituting eqn. (6) into eqn. (2) we obtain the following quadratic equation,

$$2 [HCrO_4^-]^2 + K_D[HCrO_4^-] - K_D[Cr^{VI}] = 0 \quad (7)$$

whose physically meaningful solution is

$$[HCrO_4^-] = \frac{1}{4} [(K_D^2 + 8K_D[Cr^{VI}])^{1/2} - K_D] \quad (8)$$

The concentrations of $HCrO_4^-$ reported in Table 1 are calculated from eqn. (8).

For the sake of simplicity it is considered that the only active oxidation species is $HCrO_4^-$ and it participates in the rate-limiting step. The representative reaction scheme is,

Scheme 1

where, S is a substrate (organic or inorganic) being oxidized. The rate of reaction from Scheme 1 is obtained as

$$-\frac{d[Cr^{VI}]}{dt} = k_1[HCrO_4^-] \quad (9)$$

where, k_1 is the first order rate constant and contains the concentration terms of the substrate and H^+ and K_D the equilibrium constant of the pre-equilibrium step. However, for our present purpose an exact expression of k_1 is not required because the concentrations of S and H^+ are maintained much higher than that of chromium(vi).

Now substitution of eqn. (8) into eqn. (9) gives,

$$-\frac{d[Cr^{VI}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1}{4} [(K_D^2 + 8K_D[Cr^{VI}])^{1/2} - K_D] \quad (10)$$

It may be noticed that the right-hand-side of eqn.(10) is not identical with the right-hand-side of eqn. (3), the experimental expression. But we can still define,

$$k_{exp} = \frac{k_1}{4} \frac{[(K_D^2 + 8K_D[Cr^{VI}])^{1/2} - K_D]}{[Cr^{VI}]} \quad (11)$$

and then enquire if the right-hand-side of eqn. (11) could remain constant as the reaction progresses. To answer this, we differentiate eqn. (11) with respect to time t , which gives,

$$\frac{dk_{exp}}{dt} = \frac{k_1 K_D}{4[Cr^{VI}]^2} \left(\frac{4[Cr^{VI}]}{K_D} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{X}}(\sqrt{X} - 1) \right) \frac{d[Cr^{VI}]}{dt} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{where, } X = 1 + \frac{8}{K_D} [Cr^{VI}] \quad (13)$$

It may be noted that k_{exp} can remain constant during the course of a kinetic run only when the terms within the parentheses of eqn. (12) vanish, that is when,

$$\frac{4[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{K_D} = (X - X^{1/2}) \quad (14)$$

The combination of eqns. (8), (13) and (14) produces the following quadratic equation,

$$4[\text{HCrO}_4^-]^2 + K_D[\text{HCrO}_4^-] - K_D[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] = 0 \quad (15)$$

Clearly eqn. (15) contradicts eqn. (7) with which we started and hence, in general, k_{exp} cannot remain constant with the progress of the reaction. This is a rigorous proof.

Therefore, we need to answer that how one obtains a fairly constant values of k_{exp} for a single run up to 70% of the conversion. This experimental observation can only be rationalized in terms of an average experimental rate constant, $\langle k_{\text{exp}} \rangle$, defined as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = \langle k_{\text{exp}} \rangle [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] \quad (16)$$

The instantaneous value of k_{exp} is obtained from eqns. (3) and (9) as

$$k_{\text{exp}} = \frac{[\text{HCrO}_4^-]}{[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]} k_1 \quad (17)$$

where, k_1 is the true rate constant and may be defined as

$$\langle k_{\text{exp}} \rangle = \frac{(k_{\text{exp}} [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}])_0 - (k_{\text{exp}} [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}])_t}{[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_0 - [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_t} \quad (18)$$

and the k_{corr} gets the following expression,

$$\langle k_{\text{corr}} \rangle = \langle k_{\text{exp}} \rangle \frac{[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_0}{[\text{HCrO}_4^-]_0} \quad (19)$$

The results of our calculations are depicted in Table 1. The data reveal the following : (a) $\langle k_{\text{corr}} \rangle$ are obtained smaller than the true rate constant k_1 but the discrepancy is within 5–10%, (b) $\langle k_{\text{corr}} \rangle$ value decreases with increase in $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ but the said variation is within 5–10%, and (c) $\langle k_{\text{corr}} \rangle$ for 75% conversion are around 3% higher than the corresponding values for the 50% conversion.

However, the above discrepancies and variations become significant only when our experimental rate constants are within an error limit of 3%. In majority of cases in the range of concentration of chromium(vi) of Table 1, the

titrimetric methods are employed to monitor the reaction. The accuracy of the rate constant so obtained usually lies between 5 to 15%. Hence, all experimental calculations of k_{corr} may be taken as the fairly constant values and the values themselves are pretty close to the true rate constant. To test the above predictions one needs to go for, say spectrophotometric data within the range of concentration of chromium(vi) of Table 1. At present no such data are available and hence no comparison can be attempted.

Concluding remarks :

The analysis of the present discussion for the first time reveals why one gets fairly good liner first order plots in the case of chromic acid oxidations, in spite of the fact that the rate constant in principle should increase with the progress of the reaction. Further, the common practice of obtaining the k_{corr} surprisingly produces the rate constant values very close to the true rate constant. This analysis should serve to boost the confidence of the experimental kineticists in the field of chromic acid oxidations. Now it is up to the experimentalist to use the full range of chromium(vi) concentration or to limit below $2 \times 10^{-3} M$.

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